

PRODUCTION AND PHYSICAL AND MECHANICAL CHARACTERIZATION OF LIGHTWEIGHT BIOCONCRETES USING COFFEE HUSK *Coffea arabica*

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ABSTRACT

This research aimed at the physical and chemical characterization of the *Coffea arabica* coffee husk, and its use as an aggregate for lightweight bio concrete production, measuring its mechanical properties and thermal conductivity. The coffee husk's chemical composition and basic density were evaluated. The bioaggregate was subjected to a pre-treatment in hot water at 80°C and immersion in calcium hydroxide solution. The bio concrete matrix was produced with Portland Cement CPV-ARI, metakaolin, and fly ash, with a water/cementitious material ratio of 0.35 and 3% calcium chloride about the cement mass.

KEYWORDS

Coffee husks; Bioaggregate; Bioconcrete; Lignocellulosics materials.

INTRODUCTION

The civil construction sector is responsible for using a large part of natural resources and depositing an exorbitant amount of waste in the environment. It is estimated that civil construction uses more than 50% of the planet's natural resources, most of which are non-renewable. In addition to generating more than 500 (kg) inhabitants per year of construction and demolition waste, the amount of waste produced in the extraction and processing of materials must also be added to this value, which there are no estimates provided (CBS, 2009; Isaia, 2017).

Therefore, cement-based composite materials emerge as possible solutions to reduce environmental impacts in the construction sector. Materials that use cementitious materials instead of cement and use as aggregates are unconventional raw materials such as agro-industry and forestry, construction, and demolition waste (Lima et. al., 2019; Da Gloria et al., 2020; Silva et al., 2019). In the literature, there are several studies on the use of lignocellulosic residues in the production of cement composites, an alternative of great interest to the civil construction industry, due to the lower cost of producing these materials and the reduction in the use of non-renewable resources (Souza et al., 2014; Freire et. al., 2011; Silva et. al., 2018; Soares et. al., 2017; Lima et al., 2012; Ferreira et al., 2020).

Brazil, as one of the largest agricultural producers in the world, consequently has a large amount of agro-industry residues that are improperly disposed of, which can cause several environmental problems. The environmental concern and the decrease in natural resources, encourage the search for alternatives to take advantage of these materials as raw materials for the production of bio concrete (Santos, 2020; Caldas et al., 2019).

In this context, coffee is an agricultural product that generates a large amount of solid waste in its production, the husk, which is the first waste generated in the processing of the fruit, represents about 41% of the coffee fruit (Borém, 2008). However, there are few studies related to the use of this residue, and most of them are studies focused on the production of organic fertilizers. This makes the study of

coffee husks a source of raw material for the production of innovative materials for civil construction, especially in the Southeast region, with the states of Minas Gerais and São Paulo being the largest coffee producers in the country (Vegro et al., 1994; Coffee in Brazil, 2017).

Thus, the objective of this study is to develop lightweight bio concretes with the incorporation of Coffea arabica coffee husks as an aggregate, through the characterization of Coffea arabica coffee husks, and analysis of the physical and mechanical properties of coffee husk bio concretes and the use of this residue in the civil construction as an alternative material.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

The bio concretes were produced using Coffea arabica coffee husks, supplied by Agência InovaCafé on the campus of the Federal University of Lavras – UFLA, located in the municipality of Lavras, in the southern region of Minas Gerais. The coffee husk first underwent a drying process in an open environment in the sun for 3 days. This process was carried out to remove free water and prevent its fermentation.

High initial strength CP V cement, metakaolinite, and fly ash were also used, aiming to improve the performance of mechanical properties, durability, and useful life of bio concretes and anhydrous calcium chloride P.A to compensate for the negative effect on the cement hydration promoted by the sugars present in the husks.

Physical and chemical characterization of Coffea arabica coffee husks

The basic density of the husk and the water absorption was obtained through a modified procedure mentioned in the NBR 11941 standard (ABNT, 2003). The material was submerged in water until its saturation, followed by the measurement of its mass and volume. After 72 hours in the oven at 103 ± 2 °C, its dry mass was measured.

To determine the chemical composition, the material was ground in a knife mill and sieved to obtain particles between 0.25 and 0.40 mm for the complete reaction to the reagents used in chemical analyses, according to the NBR 14660 standard (ABNT, 2004). The extractives and insoluble lignin content were obtained following the standard established by NBR 7989 (ABNT, 2010).

The determination of ash contents followed the parameters set out in the NBR 13999 standard (ABNT, 2017). To obtain the holocellulose content, the difference was made in the other molecular and mineral components of the biomass.

Bioaggregate treatment

Washing the coffee husk in heated water was used as a treatment to improve the chemical compatibility between the cement and the husk (Andreola, 2017). The coffee husk has a large number of nutrients, such as potassium, which may require more than one wash. The number of washes needed was observed through the color difference in each cycle. In this research, washing in hot water at 80 °C for one hour was used, using the ratio of 1 g/60 ml between particle mass and water volume (Ferreira et al., 2020). And the second wash in alkaline solution with calcium hydroxide for 2 hours, using 1.85 g/l between calcium hydroxide mass and water volume and a water/peel mass ratio of 10, as proposed by (Da Gloria et al. al., 2020).

FT-IR Spectroscopy – Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR)

The FTIR-ATR assays were used to evaluate the efficiency of the bioaggregate washing processes. For this test, samples of particles in their natural state were analyzed, with 1, 2, and 3 washes in hot water.

Through the method, Fourier Transform Infrared Spectroscopy (ATR-FTIR) coupled to an attenuated total reflection (ATR) accessory using an FTIR Spectrometer Varian 600-IR Series equipped with GladiATR from Pike Technologies for FTIR-ATR measurements, samples of coffee husk particles with

a maximum particle size of 0.250 mm. Samples were scanned from 4000 to 400 cm⁻¹ with 32 averaged scans per spectrum with a resolution of 4 cm⁻¹.

Bioconcrete production

According to previous studies on bio concretes the use of Brazilian Portland cement of high initial strength CPV-ARI, together with pozzolanic materials, metakaolinite, and fly ash, as binders, generated good results (Da Gloria et al., 2020; Andreola et al., 2019). The chemical composition and density of cementitious materials can be verified in Table 1, as found by (Andreola, 2017). Table 2, on the other hand, presents the dosage per cubic meter of bio concrete.

Table 1: Chemical composition and density of cementitious materials.

Chemical elements	Cement (%)	MTK (%)	Fly ash (%)
CaO	69,97	-	1,95
SiO ₂	14,96	50,95	52,25
Al ₂ O ₃	4,70	42,22	33,81
Fe ₂ O ₃	3,51	1,98	4,91
K ₂ O	0,99	1,98	3,44
SO ₃	4,30	1,20	1,79
SrO	0,42	0,01	0,02
MnO	014	0,01	0,04
ZnO	0.01	0,01	0,04
Density (g/cm³)	3,17	2,81	2,16

Table 2: Dosing of bio concrete.

Bio concrete	Coffee husk	Cement	Fly ash	MTK	H₂O_{hidr}	H₂O_{comp}	CaCl₂
BCC45-0.35	164.61	241.03	321.38	241.03	281.20	96.29	24.10

For the production of composites, a water/cement materials ratio of 0.35 was used (Andreola et al., 2019). Using the volumetric fraction of 45% of coffee husk, similar to the substitution ratios of 40%, 45%, and 50% (Da Gloria, 2020). It is necessary to compensate for the volume of water absorbed by the biomass to ensure the consistency of the bio concrete (Silveira et al., 2018; Andreola, 2017). Thus, 180% of make-up water was used about the mass of the bioaggregate, based on previous studies, considerably improving the workability of the bio concrete. 3% of calcium chloride was also used to accelerate the hydration of the cement.

The procedures for the bio concrete production process were based on the study by Da Glória (2020), it first in a separate container the water and calcium chloride are mixed. Then, in the planetary mixer (20 liters) the cementitious materials are mixed for 1 minute, then the husk is added and the mixture is mixed for 1 min, with the progressive addition of water for 1 minute. A 30-second pause to remove materials that may stick to the bottom. The mixture must be done for another 1 minute for total homogenization of the bio concrete.

Thus, the mixture is placed in molds already lubricated with mineral oil, and 3 layers are added. The layers were compacted on a vibrating table (68 Hz) for 10 seconds. The specimens were protected so as not to lose moisture and kept in the mold for 24 hours. Finally, the specimens were taken to a dry chamber at 21 ± 2 °C and relative humidity of 60%, until they reached 28 days of age.

Dry curing was used, according to the results of Silva (2019) who showed that bio concretes have higher mechanical strength when subjected to dry curing compared to wet curing.

Physical and mechanical characterization of bio concrete

The consistency of the bio concretes is evaluated in the fresh state, which consists of an evaluation to validate the dosing method, the experiment is done in a flow table test. The consistency index was obtained through the average of the scattering diameters, according to the one developed by (Andreola, 2017). The apparent density of the bio concretes was obtained by weighing them after 28 days of dry curing, using the mass/volume ratio, as in the study by (Da Gloria, 2020).

The uniaxial compression tests followed the standards proposed by NBR 5739 (ABNT, 2018). Tests were performed for the ages of 7 and 28 days. To perform the tests, a Shimadzu-1000 kN model machine was used at a displacement speed of 0.3 mm /min. The vertical displacements were measured using the average reading of two LVDTs variable linear transformers. Finally, the modulus of elasticity was determined using the method provided for in the NBR 8522 standard (ABNT, 2021).

Thermal conductivity test

For the thermal conductivity tests, the TCi thermal conductivity analyzer was used, manufactured by the company C-Therm Technologies, with a testing capacity from 0 to 500 W/Mk in a temperature range from -50°C to 200°C. For the bio concrete of this research, the Low K program module was used, with analysis settings for materials such as foams, plastics, ceramics, and composites (K-Range from 0 to 10 W/mK). This equipment uses a one-sided, interfacial heat reflectance sensor that momentarily applies a constant heat source to the sample. 6 readings were made for each specimen, the first reading was taken, and then the average between the 5 remaining values was taken to obtain the final result.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Physical and chemical characterization of Coffea arabica coffee husks

In Figure 1, it is possible to observe in b) that the coffee husk is composed of 2 main elements: the external husk (exocarp) and the parchment (endocarp) the inner part of the husk. And in c) we have the granulometric curve of the raw material used.

a) Coffee tree with ripe fruit.

b) Ripe coffee fruit.

c) Coffee husk granulometric curve.

Figure 1: Coffee tree *Coffea arabica* in a), coffee fruit in b) and granulometric curve in c).

It is possible to observe through the granulometric curve that the particles present: D_{90} equal to 4.75 mm, D_{50} equal to 1.8 mm, and D_{10} equal to 0.40 mm.

The quantification of the chemical components found in the natural coffee husk, with 1, 2, and 3 washes, is shown in Table 3.

Table 3: Chemical components found in *Coffea arabica* coffee husks with different washes.

Components (%)	Chemical Characterization			
	Natural husk	1 wash	2 washes	3 washes
Lignina	23,47	26,94	27,94	19,42
Holocelulose	12,23	41,86	52,61	66,58
Cinzas	17,30	8,70	6,70	2,45
Extrativos	47,00	22,50	12,75	11,55

Lignin has hydrophobic properties, giving the material impermeability, which makes it known as a natural adhesive. It acts to reinforce the cellulose microfibrils, which reduces movements perpendicular to the grain and contributes to mechanical and biological resistance (Silva et al., 2018; Neutelings, 2011). Therefore, higher lignin contents such as those found are interesting for application, for example, in the production of reconstituted wood panels.

We can observe that holocellulose has a lower content in the natural coffee husk compared to the contents after the biomass has been washed. Holocellulose and consequently hemicellulose are components that have chemical binding sites with water (Freire et al., 2011; Scatolino et al., 2017).

Thus, lower levels of holocellulose and hemicellulose demonstrate that the material absorbs less water. Regarding the amount of ash, coffee husks have high ash contents when compared to some woods in the literature, which can be explained by their low-density material, as found in some types of wood (Klock; Andrade, 2013). Natural husk has a large number of extractives compared to other lignocellulosic materials found in the literature, for example, some woods (Klock; Andrade, 2013; Soares et al., 2017). Extractives are components that have characteristics that can increase the water resistance of the bioaggregate, when higher values are found in lignocellulosic materials it can mean the loss of permeability and its hygroscopic property (Scatolino et al., 2017).

The natural husk presented 47% in extractives, when we washed the husk 1 time this percentage dropped considerably to 22.50%, which represents a difference of 24.50% fewer extractives, in the second washing we obtained a smaller reduction, of 9.75% and in the third a much smaller reduction, of only 1.2%.

The high content of extractives is a characteristic that leads to the need for initial treatment of the husk as proposed by (Da Gloria, 2020; Andreola et al., 2019). Finally, we can see in the last 3 columns that the hot water treatment was effective for the reduction of extractives, which allowed us to verify that 2 washes would be enough to treat the raw material.

Table 4 shows the values found for basic density, moisture content, water absorption, and apparent specific mass of the coffee husk in its natural state.

Table 4: Physical characterization of *Coffea arabica* coffee husks.

Basic density (g/cm^3)	Moisture content (%)	Water absorption (%)	Apparent Specific mass (g/cm^3)
1,50	10,23	176,50	0,41

As we can see, values of 0.41 g/cm³ were found for the apparent density, 10.23% for the moisture content, and 176.50% for the material's water absorption. The apparent density found is similar to the apparent density of some woods found in the literature (Da Gloria et al., 2020; Silveira et al., 2018). The coffee husk can be considered a low-density material, the results found are satisfactory and represents the high internal porosity of the material, as the proposed classification for low-density materials (Beraldo, 2011).

FT-IR Spectroscopy – Attenuated Total Reflectance (ATR)

FTIR is an analysis that can be performed to study possible modifications in the fibers of the bioaggregate according to the treatment used (Hoyos, 2013). The graph in Figure 2 shows the FTIR peaks of natural coffee husks, and with 3 types of washes.

We can observe some main peaks in natural coffee husks and after washing, such as the peak of 3315 cm⁻¹ that represents the vibrations of hydrogen of -OH groups of alcohols, phenols or carboxylic acids, and of amides; the peak of 2931 cm⁻¹ refers to the elongation of the -OH bond in the methyl and methylene groups and of vibrations -CH of aliphatic groups; the peak of 1734 cm⁻¹ is given as the C=O elongation of aldehydes, ketones, and carboxylic acids of the lignin backbone; peaks in the region of 1599 cm⁻¹ have characteristics of secondary amides, and show C=C vibrations of aromatic structures and C=O groups associated with an aromatic ring; the peak at 1375 cm⁻¹ is characteristic of absorption of some aliphatic structures, phenolic OH groups, COO-, N-H groups of amides, aromatic rings and carbonates; the 1245 cm⁻¹ peak characteristic of the C-O-C bond elongation of ether groups; and the 1021 cm⁻¹ peak characteristic of silicate, ether and aromatic ester groups and C-O elongation of polysaccharides (Hoyos, 2013; Jouraiphy et al (2005); Parravicini et al., 2006; Deepa et al., 2015).

Figure 2: Peaks of the FTIR analysis referring to coffee husks with different washes.

It is possible to observe in Table 5 that the peaks of 2931 and 2856 cm⁻¹ of the natural bark, were found in all the FTIR spectra of the different samples, they were decreasing according to each wash, presenting similar peaks for each treatment, being them characteristic to the presence of fat and lipids, aliphatic compounds and methylene groups; peaks at 1600 cm⁻¹ are typical of woods, fruits, grasses, and other

plants; and the peak at 1599 cm^{-1} refers to a protein (Grube et al., 2006). Lignin is characterized by a spectrum around 1510 to 1460 cm^{-1} referring to the structure of the aromatic lignin skeleton (Fengel and Wegener, 1989).

The coffee husk has some typical and well-defined peaks, as can be seen in Figure 3. The band of 3315 cm^{-1} is characterized by the O-H bond representing the amount of water present in each sample. It also presents the spectra between 1599 and 770 cm^{-1} , specific for C=C bonds, linked to vibrations of aromatic rings, and flavonoid compounds found in tannins and stretches =COC=, of oxo-aromatic composition, among other components.

Workability of bio concrete

Figure 3 shows the typical scattering obtained from the specimens of the studied bio concrete. We can see that the samples showed no exudation. Da Glória (2020) proposes consistency indexes above 190 mm for the mixture to have good workability. The average consistency index of 180 mm was lower than that proposed in the literature. However, the samples did not present difficulties to be placed in the molds and presented a homogeneous mixture with workability.

The result is similar to others in the literature that use wood or cereal husks with a matrix of cementitious materials containing cement, metakaolinite, and fly ash. Da Glória (2020) found bio concretes with 45% sawdust and a water/cement material ratio of 0.35, a spread of 180 mm. Santos (2020) found for bio concretes with 45% rice husk, and a water/cement material ratio of 0.69, the value for spreading of 180 mm.

a) Specimen 1 BCC45. b) Specimen 2 BCC45. c) Specimen 3 BCC45.

Figure 3: Spreading of three samples of the studied bio concrete.

Physical and mechanical characterization of bio concrete

The average density obtained from the bio concretes was 1.19 g/cm^3 . According to the Functional Classification of Rilem (1978), we can classify bio concrete with coffee husks as light concrete, and densities lower than 1.80 g/cm^3 are recommended.

The coffee husk bio concretes were demolded after 24 hours, which demonstrates that the treatment of the bioaggregate and the addition of calcium chloride are efficient to prevent the delay or inhibit the hydration reactions of the cement. The bio concretes were subjected to uniaxial compression tests after 7 and 28 days of age, as shown in the typical stress x deformation curves of bio concrete in the graph in Figure 4. The compression tests of bio concrete present a linear phase and then enter a non-linear phase until reaching the peak stress, just after the peak, it presents a low decrease in stress with increasing strain. There is little variation in stress after reaching the peak stress, which suggests a slow crack propagation, possibly due to a large amount of coffee husk.

Figure 4: Typical stress vs strain curves of bio concrete subjected to compression.

Table 5 shows the maximum values of stress and deformation found for the tests with 7 and 28 days, and the modulus of elasticity. For the uniaxial compression tests with 7 and 28 days, he found compressive strength values of 1.23 MPa and 1.16 MPa, respectively. According to the normative parameters, the values of 0.38 GPa and 0.36 GPa were determined for the modulus of elasticity for 7 and 28 days of age, respectively. Another important point is the homogeneity of the material. Even using a high number of bioaggregate, the bio concrete presented a good visual appearance and good distribution of particles in the sample. This good distribution is compatible with concrete compressive strength results, especially at 28 days (2.58%).

Table 5: Mechanical properties of bio concretes.

Age (days)	Compressive Strength (MPa)	Strain ($\mu\epsilon$)	E (GPa)
7	$1,23 \pm 0,26$	$38617,05 \pm 8874,91$	$0,38 \pm 0,37$
28	$1,16 \pm 0,03$	$38122,93 \pm 4727,49$	$0,36 \pm 0,09$

The bio concretes after 28 days showed a drop in compressive strength of 5.69% about that obtained with 7 days, which can be explained by the volume of biomass used in the mixture and its high water absorption content, which can cause greater shrinkage, that is, as the particle absorbed a greater water content by capillarity in the presence of a greater volume of shell in the bio concrete, consequently, there was a release of free water in the same proportion. Thus, the composite may have suffered mass loss and increased porosity, causing a higher void ratio, thus influencing the decrease in strength after 28 days of age, studies (Ferreira, 2012; Da Gloria, 2015).

The results found are similar to others in the literature, which used wood and cereal husks. Da Glória (2020) found, in 28-day trials, for bio concrete with pozzolanic matrix replacing 50% sawdust and 0.45 w/mc ratio, the values of 1.15 MPa for compressive strength and 1.92 Compressive strength MPa for 50% sawdust and 0.40 w/mc ratio. In their study, it was possible to observe that greater biomass substitutions and greater water/cement materials ratios tend to decrease the compressive strength of bio concrete and pozzolanic matrices have greater sensitivity when there is an increase in water hydration than bio concrete produced with cement matrix. Santos (2020), made bio concretes with percentages of biomass replacement of 45%, 50%, and 52% and a w/c ratio of 0.64, 0.69, and 0.75 using all the ratios for each type of substitution, finding values for compressive strength from 0.21 to 3.15 MPa and elastic modulus from 0.25 to 1.88 GPa. Therefore, in this study, it was possible to observe that with higher values of bioaggregate replacement and water/cement ratio, and lower cement consumption, there is a decrease in compressive strength and modulus of elasticity.

In Figure 5, the specimens are arranged after a uniaxial compression test, which shows similar patterns in the rupture of the specimens, and it is possible to observe in the third image that even with a large amount of shell in the composite, the rupture distribution occurred in a proportional across the specimen.

a) Specimens BCC45. b) Specimen BCC45. c) Broken specimen.

Figure 5: Bio concrete after compression test in a) image of specimens after the compression test, in b) image of only one specimen and its cracks and c) broken specimen.

Thermal conductivity

The average thermal conductivity obtained from the bio concretes was 0.32 W/mk. The result presented by the coffee husk bio concretes has a higher thermal conductivity than some woods, and the composites with rice husk and light cement matrix by Pachla (2019) also have similarities to the values found by Da Glória (2015) who use sawdust as a bioaggregate and is less conductive than cement paste.

Da Glória (2015) obtained thermal conductivity results for bio concretes with wood sawdust contents of 45%, 50 and 60%, between 0.06 – 0.53 W/mK. According to data presented in his work, wood has thermal conduction of 0.08 to 0.23 W/Mk and cement paste from 0.6 to 1.2 W/mK. Pachla (2019) found, that for light cement matrix and composite with rice husk with 35% of the biomass, thermal conductivity values of 0.24 and 0.27 W/mK, respectively. Aguiar (2020), carried out a study of the effects of the addition of wood sawdust on the thermal conductivity of bio concrete with contents of 40%, 50%, and 60% and obtained results of 0.47 – 0.29 W/mK, also noting that thermal conductivity tends to decrease with increasing biomass and decreasing density. The thermal conductivity or matrix porosity is influenced by factors such as the age of the composite, the number of aggregates used, part of cement, portion of fines, water/cement ratio, additive used, humidity, and sample preparation method, among others (Kim et al., 2003), but it can also consider the additional porosity that the biomass can generate in the mixing process (Aguiar, 2020).

CONCLUSION

The coffee husk, as for its chemical characterization, presents lignin, holocellulose, ash, and extractive contents, similar to the chemical compounds found in wood, in its natural state it has a high content of extractives and lignin when compared, for example, with some woods, when this bark goes through a pre-treatment there is a significant reduction in the number of extractives and the lignin shows low

variation. A higher lignin content may have an advantage as it may decrease the permeability of the material, a good characteristic for applications in particleboard panels. The biomass has a low density and can be compared to wood with lower densities.

The FTIR analysis shows typical peaks that indicate the presence of water in the particles, as well as the existence of vibrations of aromatic rings, fats, lipids, proteins, and peaks characteristic of wood, fruits, and plants.

The treatment of the bioaggregate with a wash in hot water and a second wash in alkaline immersion proved to be more efficient than two washes in hot water. This allows the reduction of energy used in heating the water.

In relation to the bio concretes, the use of CPV-ARI cement together with the addition of calcium chloride and the treatment used to the residue, to ensure the hydration of the cement and its hardening, allowed the demoulding of the specimens within 24 hours. The combination of fly ash and metakaolinite allowed a replacement of 70% of the cement mass in the mixture. It was found for 7 and 28 days of age, the value of 1.19 g/cm³ for density and for compressive strength was 1.23 MPa in 7 days and 1.16 MPa in 28 days.

Finally, the objective of this work to produce light bio concrete had a positive result, the final products presented low density. Furthermore, the bio concretes obtained good physical, workability, and thermal conductivity properties. Their mechanical properties, despite having low strength, had a good crack propagation behavior and little variation in stress with increasing strain after the highest stress peak.

Therefore, coffee husk has good properties as an alternative lignocellulosic material to apply in bio concrete. And it proved to be a material with the potential to be used in the production of new products for the civil construction industry in Brazil.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.